

REFERENTIAL PECULIARITIES OF MODALITY

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Abstract. Peculiarities modality and its referential aspects, its features based on tense and depended on the speaker's information viewpoint and the syntactic model of sentence creation is defined.

Key words: denotative-subject content, intention, topic-rhematic structure of the utterance, predication, referent, discourse.

Introduction. Any statement that includes subjective content—an expression of the speaker's opinion about a particular object or event—in addition to its denotative-subject content—a proposition in which nominations of objects of reality are fixed and a reference to them is established—is recognized as modal. This leads us to the conclusion that the statement realizes two fundamentally different types of semantics: 1) referential (world reflection, fixation of nominations of objects of reality in the sentence structure), and 2) modal (depiction of the speaker's attitude toward the entirety of the events he describes, subjective evaluation and characterization of actions, their performers, and accompanying circumstances). Certain lexical and grammatical constructions can serve both referential (referential) and modal (evaluative) purposes in a sentence, making the distinction between a sentence's modal and referential semantics somewhat arbitrary. The majority of sentences' structures, however, provide for a clear difference between the referential-factual and subjective-modal plans of content, notwithstanding their complexity. For instance: *Sarah was dumb enough to pretend that she wasn't at hotel where I saw her yesterday.* In addition to portraying the event—Sarah's pretense—as having truly occurred, this line also depicts the speaker's attitude toward the specific individual who is identified by the proper name Sarah. Thus, the predicate “*was stupid enough*” expresses the evaluative modality in this sentence, and the infinitive phrase and subordinate clause establish the reference to actual events “*wasn't at hotel where I saw her yesterday*”.

In the information aspect of assertions, many researchers frequently draw distinctions between modal (assertive) and presumptive components. Since the speaker's intention, or modality, is how information is dispersed throughout the topic-rhematic structure of the utterance—where the most crucial elements of

the message's content are disclosed—the modal portion of the utterance functions as an actualizer of the entire communicative meaning in a sense. Its constituent parts: Depending on the speaker's information viewpoint and the syntactic model of sentence creation, the nominal and verbal groups may have distinct denotative statuses, or link to reality in different ways. Therefore, some groups of nominal and predicative statements can be used in a way that is directly related to reality, i.e., with a specific reference; others can be used in a way that is non-referential, i.e., to denote an event that basically never happened; and still others can convey the speaker's various subjective-modal shades and express his opinion (confidence or assumption) about a given event.

The investigation has demonstrated that language tools of expressing modality can also serve a merely regulatory role in communication, whereby they are employed to transmit pragmatically implicit information. Modal words can have several meanings when used to stylize discourse, such as emphasizing or weakening a point or eliminating categorization: *“Your opinion of me doesn't seem to be very high.”*

As was previously mentioned, the opposition between the modal and referential aspects of linguistic units' content can be followed at two different levels: syntactically, which is the structure of a sentence or statement (dictemes); and lexico-phraseologically, which is the semantics of the individual words that comprise a statement. The truth is that important vocabulary fulfills multiple functions at once. It is a component of the speech and uses morphological and syntactic devices to structure its subject-situational meaning:

- the designation of a specific segment of reality and, as a result, the fixation in the semantics of the nominative units of the components of the displayed situation (participants in communication, situational action, temporal and spatial localization of the named event)
- predication, i.e., connecting the substantive basis of the situation named in the sentence to reality, including establishing the reference of noun phrases to the corresponding objects of extra-linguistic reality - referents;
- modalization, or the expression of the speaker's attitude toward the situation (his favorable or unfavorable evaluation of the event under discussion, his agreement or disagreement with one or more statements of the interlocutors, the speaker's confidence or his assumptions regarding the state of affairs)

Conclusion. When modal verbs, such as those in the future tense, are used, they are directly referring to the speaker. In one form or another, every remark made about the future is, more or less, an assumption made by the

speaker and is therefore justified. Future-tense dependent adjectives cannot be used referentially because the situation they designate does not yet exist in reality. Instead, they merely indicate the event, portraying it as conceivable given the current state of affairs, and more fully convey the speaker's attitude toward the situation. However, since a rationally anticipated future situation always serves as an evaluation of the current state of affairs, any statement about the future must necessarily have some reference to the present. As a result, the future is understood to be the anticipated outcomes of a specific situation that exists at the time of speech.

Many linguistic devices, including lexical, grammatical, syntactic, intonation, and complex combinations of these devices, are used to indicate modalities, which are manifestations of the speaker's attitude toward reality. As a result, when people speak, they express relationships and feelings in addition to facts and object descriptions.

However, it should be highlighted that, for the specific reference of a linguistic expression (as opposed to its truth), what matters is the speaker's confidence in the existence of the object, not its actual presence in extralinguistic reality, expressed in a statement. As a result, reference and modality are attributes of the speaker's claims about reality itself, pertaining to real and unreal events that have occurred in the past, present, and future as well as to objects that exist and those that do not. Therefore, even when the scenario being discussed is purely theoretical and not real, reference and modality are the means by which participants in a conversation can develop understanding with one another.

In general, even when there are no explicit modal markers present, the substance of an utterance retains its modal coloring. Every statement, in one form or another, contains a subjective element or the speaker's point of view; it embodies personal experience, a set of values, and the extent of general knowledge. According to I.R. Halperin, modality is present throughout the entire work: "the author's subjective and evaluative attitude towards the events and facts described can be implicit even in substantive and factual information."

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